

MAIN TYPES OF ENGLISH DICTIONARY

Baxtiyorova Nodirabegim Otabek qizi
Student, Chirchik State Pedagogical University
Okeanka2406@icloud.com

Scientific adviser:
Senior teacher: Chirchik state pedagogical university
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15693896>

ABSTRACT. This article examines the main types of English dictionaries and their significance in language learning and communication. Dictionaries serve as essential tools for understanding and using language accurately. The study categorizes English dictionaries into several types, including monolingual, bilingual, learner's dictionaries, thesauruses, and specialized dictionaries.

Keywords: English dictionaries, dictionary types, monolingual, bilingual, thesaurus, learners' dictionary, specialized dictionary.

Dictionaries have always been essential tools for language learning, communication, and academic research. They help users understand the meanings, usage, pronunciation, and origin of words. Over time, different types of dictionaries have emerged, each serving a specific purpose. English dictionaries, in particular, can be categorized into monolingual, bilingual, learners' dictionaries, thesauruses, and specialized dictionaries. Understanding these types can help individuals choose the most suitable resource for their linguistic and academic needs.

1. Monolingual dictionaries. Monolingual dictionaries provide definitions, explanations, and word usage entirely in English. They are widely used by native speakers, advanced learners, and professionals. These dictionaries offer detailed information, including word origins (etymology), pronunciation, grammatical usage, and example sentences.

Example of Monolingual dictionaries:

a) Oxford English Dictionary (OED) – Provides historical development and extensive meanings of words.

b) Merriam-Webster Dictionary – Offers definitions, pronunciation, and word trends in American English.

c) Cambridge English Dictionary – Designed for learners and general users with clear definitions.

Monolingual dictionaries are useful for developing a deeper understanding of the language and enhancing vocabulary. However, they may be challenging for beginners who need translation assistance.

2. Bilingual dictionaries. Bilingual dictionaries are designed for users who need to translate words between English and another language. These dictionaries help non-native speakers understand English words by providing equivalent meanings in their native language. Benefits of bilingual dictionaries:

- a. Facilitate quick translation between languages.
- b. Useful for beginners and travelers.
- c. Examples of bilingual dictionaries:
- d. Collins English – French dictionary
- e. Oxford Spanish – English dictionary
- f. Longman English – Chinese dictionary

Although bilingual dictionaries are beneficial for translation, they sometimes fail to capture the full meaning and nuances of words, which can lead to misunderstandings.

3. Learners' dictionaries. They are specifically designed for non-native English speakers. They provide simplified definitions, example sentences, pronunciation guides, and grammar tips. These dictionaries often use controlled vocabulary to ensure that explanations are easy to understand. Features of learners' dictionaries:

- a) Definitions in simple and clear English.
- b) Phonetic transcriptions for pronunciation assistance.
- c) Usage examples to show how words function in context.

Examples of learners' dictionaries:

- a) Oxford advanced learner's dictionary
- b) Cambridge learner's dictionary
- c) Longman dictionary of contemporary English

Learners' dictionaries are excellent resources for English language learners at all levels, as they provide a gradual introduction to complex vocabulary and grammatical structures.

4. Thesauruses. A thesaurus is a type of dictionary that provides synonyms and antonyms of words rather than definitions. It is an essential tool for writers, students and professionals who want to improve their vocabulary and avoid repetition in writing. Benefits of using a thesaurus: helps in finding synonyms and antonyms, enhances writing by providing alternative word choices, supports vocabulary development. Examples of English thesauruses:

- a) Roget's thesaurus
- b) Collins English thesaurus
- c) Merriam – Webster's thesaurus

A thesaurus is particularly useful for academic writing, creative writing, and professional communication. However, users must be careful when selecting synonyms to ensure that they fit the context correctly.

5. Specialized dictionaries. They focus on specific fields such as medicine, law, business, or science. These dictionaries provide definitions, technical terms, and explanations relevant to a particular industry or discipline. Types of specialized dictionaries:

- a) Medical dictionary – explains medical terms and conditions.(e.g.,Dorland's illustrated medical dictionary)
- b) Law dictionary – defines legal terms and concepts.(e.g.,Black's law dictionary)
- c) Business dictionary – covers business-related vocabulary.(e.g.,Oxford business English dictionary)

Specialized dictionaries are invaluable for professionals and students in specific fields, as they provide precise and accurate definitions that general dictionaries may not include.

In conclusion, English dictionaries come in various forms, each designed to serve different needs. Monolingual dictionaries provide detailed word explanations, while bilingual dictionaries help with translation. Learners' dictionaries are excellent for non - native speakers, and thesauruses assist in finding synonyms and antonyms. Specialized dictionaries cater to specific fields such as law, medicine, or business. Choosing the right type of dictionary depends on user's purpose, language proficiency, and field of study. By understanding the different types of dictionaries, individuals can improve their language skills and enhance their communication abilities effectively.

REFERENCE:

1. Black, H.C. (1999). Black's Law Dictionary (7th ed.). West Publishing
2. Cambridge University Press.(2022).Cambridge English dictionary. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org>
3. Dorland, W.A (2020). Dorland's Illustrated Medical Dictionary (33rd ed.). Elsevier.
4. Ibraximjonovna J. M. Analytical reading is the basis of integration between subjects //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 5. – С. 1114-1118.
5. Longman.(2022). Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English. Retrieved from <https://www.Idoceanline.com>.
6. Merriam –Webster. (2022).Merriam – Webster's Online Dictionary and Thesaurus. Retrieved from <https://www.merriam-webster.com>
7. Oxford University Press.(2022).Oxford English Dictionary (OED).Retrieved from <https://www.oed.com>
8. Roget. P.M. (1852).Roget's Thesaurus of English Words and Phrases. Longman.
9. Жакбарова Махлия Ибрагимжоновна (2022). Использование учебных заданий в развитии речевых навыков учащихся. Образование и инновационные исследования 12(1), 225-231.

